

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: YEBOAH****FIRST NAME: CHARLES****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical /in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MS Word Office 365 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)

1. The elements of writing academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 7-11)
2. Some suggested rules for writing academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 12-24)
3. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 18)
4. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 25)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34,37)
6. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 41)

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

It is a pleasure to be admitted into Euclid University and pursue the first course, International Academic and Professional Paper Writing (ACA-401/401D). This course will prepare me to write good essays for course assignments and dissertations at EUCLID and for any academic and professional work I will do after graduating from this University.

After my enrollment at EUCLID, I surfed the University's website to be acquainted with the program and other pertinent information. It is worth mentioning that EUCLID commits itself to structured academic writing and critical thinking as the core of its educational philosophy.

So far, I have printed the student orientation information document (as advised by the University) and placed the other relevant documents, including the coursepack, in one folder for easy access. Furthermore, I have familiarized myself with the assigned videos, so I am ready to begin this first course (and other subsequent courses) on a good note.

I highly commend Prof. Laurent Cleenewerk and Dr. Kabiru Gulma for compiling the notes for the ACA-401/401D course as well as the “How to Write a Response Paper” document (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021). The ACA-401D coursepack is in-depth material with many important topics to learn to enhance one's essay writing. The elaboration on templates, rules of style, logical flow, structuring headers, and mode of reference is enlightening. Though I have a good command of the English language (both oral and written), I realize that I still need to learn new concepts (grammar, punctuation, etc.) from this course and reinforce the ones I already know. I am sure that these invaluable course notes will also help the students of EUCLID to improve their writing skills.

In this response paper, I am discussing the elements of academic essays, some suggested rules for writing academic essays, punctuations, American vs. British English, plagiarism, and a style guide.

2) THE ELEMENTS OF WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAYS

An academic essay is a structured non-fictional form of writing that aims to convey evidence-based ideas to stated hypotheses. It is produced as part of academic work and could be published in journals, books, newspapers, or monographs or remain as theses, dissertations, or manuscripts (EUCLID 2021, 7). Thus, I realized that a scholarly paper is used to disseminate information to its readers; hence it should be written in a universally accepted manner.

I gathered that it is essential to plan one's essay. Scholarly writing with no plan is like building a house with no architectural design, as one will not know the appropriate materials to use, the time to complete the building, and the space the building will occupy, for example. That is to say that planning what one will write helps one know how to begin, proceed, and end the essay with all the required information about the topic under discussion. I found that, in summary, a plan outlines the steps to follow for the write-up of the essay, which invariably serves as the structure or the framework of one's scholarly paper.

I noted that the writer should embark on research by reading about the topic or the question of the essay to have enough evidence to support the subject under discussion after he or she has designed the plan. Information such as summaries, direct quotes from texts, case studies, or statistics with bibliographic details such as author's name, date, title, publisher, place of publication, and other relevant information (EUCLID 2021, 8-9), should be taken note of during the writer's research.

Using the written down plan and the information obtained through research, the writer must produce a draft of the essay comprising mainly the introduction, body, and conclusion and reference the work appropriately to avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 10). In addition, an essay should be edited several times to correct errors and to ensure that the arguments address the topic well.

3) SOME SUGGESTED RULES FOR WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAYS

According to (EUCLID 2021, 13), mentioning the central thesis in the opening paragraph or the introduction is essential when writing academic essays. I believe this gives the reader an overview of what the writer will discuss in the body of the paper. Thus, clearly stating the main idea this way serves as a guide for the entire essay.

I concur that one should stay focused and describe the relevant aspect(s) of the theory being assessed in scholarly papers (EUCLID 2021, 13). In my opinion, providing a detailed review of the thesis may seem confusing and boring. So, one should concisely clarify the parts of the argument that seem more informative and captivating.

Writers are also advised to avoid generalizations or sweeping statements (EUCLID 2021, 13) as they may not be able to be substantiated with proof or evidence. Moreover, as clichés are words or phrases that are overused, not interesting, and show a lack of original thought, I think they should not be incorporated into scholarly papers.

Clarity of thought and expressions should be adhered to in essays, avoiding lengthy and complicated sentences. The link between sentences should be understandable, and paragraphs should logically follow from one before it. That means there should be a flow or connection from one point to the other. Moreover, stylish varieties of expressing ideas need to be introduced in academic papers to avoid boredom. The essay writer should avoid redundancy and use synonymous words instead of repeating a word or word in essays.

For an essay to be more reliable and devoid of plagiarism, the assertions should be supported with relevant evidence; for example, when one attributes views to the person whose ideas one is addressing, one needs to indicate the evidence for the attribution by noting relevant passages (EUCLID 2021, 12-14).

4) PUNCTUATIONS

I am fascinated that the topic "punctuations" is covered under the ACA-401/401D course, as I have not entirely understood the application of some punctuations, especially bullet points, colons, and semicolons. I try to avoid their usage in my essays in conformity with the statement that "use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence" (EUCLID 2021, 16). However, after reading the assigned notes, I am now conversant with how they are employed in essays. Notwithstanding this assertion, I will review them periodically to refresh my understanding of their usage.

Three rules I have noted about the use of bullet points are that (i) bullet points which are a list of items, must not be punctuated; (ii) if the bullet points form a complete sentence with a preceding text, one must add a full stop to the end of the last point and (iii) if a text inside the bullet point is a complete sentence in its own right, a semicolon must be added

to the end of each point, 'or' or 'and' (depending on the sense of your sentence) to the end of the penultimate point, and a full stop to the end of the last one (EUCLID 2021, 18).

Regarding the use of a colon, one does not use a colon if the two parts of the sentence are not logically connected (EUCLID 2021, 18).

A semicolon links two related parts of a sentence, neither of which depends logically on the other, and each could stand alone as a grammatically complete sentence. Furthermore, semicolons are used in place of commas in a complicated list or sentence to improve clarity, particularly if list items already include commas (EUCLID 2021, 18).

In a nutshell, I recommend that one studies the use of all the punctuations, especially the use of bullet points, colon, and semicolon, to avoid being mixed up with and making errors in their applications when writing scholarly papers.

5) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

I have gathered that neither American nor British English is superior. EUCLID (2021, 25) indicates that they are both variants of World English and that they are more similar than different, especially with "educated" or "scientific" English. Either British or American English could be used for a scholarly essay (Cleenewerck, 2021)

Notwithstanding their similarities, I will stick to the use of American English as it currently dominates the world due to the growth of the United States' political, economic, technological, and cultural influence, among others.

6) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is using a source of information without giving proper credit to the author of that source of information. Plagiarism is wrong and unethical. It is unfair to take someone's work and not give him or her credit. This serious academic offense can have serious consequences (EUCLID 2021, 34).

Plagiarism is a fraud as the writers consider the ideas as their own. I would be honest and recognize the work of authors because not acknowledging someone's contribution to a journal, book or any published work is like not saying "thank you" to someone who has given you a precious gift. Someone might have toiled and come up with important information or an idea to solve a problem. If one fails to recognize that work with an appropriate reference or bibliography is ungrateful, in my opinion.

Common knowledge or facts known by many people need not be cited. Examples are as follows: (i) when you throw a ball up, it returns to the earth; (ii) the current President of the United States is John Biden, and (iii) DNA is the genetic material of living organisms.

7) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide documents one's approach to some aspects of writing style that need consistency. EUCLID recommends using the Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognized Rules are also accepted (EUCLID 2021, 41).

A style guide ensures that contributing authors of an article, for example, follow a standard that does not carry a personal writing style. Moreover, a style guide comprises many features, including a particular language (e.g., American vs. British English), font size, symbols, abbreviations, terminology, and length of sentences.

I am glad to learn this writing style because I have never used it before. I will be acquainted with using this style after applying it several times in my essays at Euclid University.

8) CONCLUSION

I am thrilled to pursue this International Academic Writing course and be introduced to many elements that enhance scholarly writing. The lessons on punctuation, style guides, American vs. British English, avoiding plagiarism, and other topics are comprehensive and thought-provoking. I congratulate EUCLID for ensuring that students pursue this course to equip them with the rudiments of producing standard academic papers.

I will use the knowledge I have acquired in this course, ACA-401/401D, to improve my essay writing.

REFERENCES

- Cleenewerck, Laurent, dir. 2021. *The Assigned Study Material (Video) Is: Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Accessed November 9, 2022.
<https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.
- Cleenewerk, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui: Euclid University.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Fourth Edition*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed.* Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.